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Deliverable 3.5 P2Green Videogame

Closing the gap between fork and farm for circular nutrient flows

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1 P2Green Videogame

The document is divided into five subsections: “Game overview,” “Gameplay mechanics,” “Story and setting,” “Technical specifications,” and “Conclusions.” The first three subsections present the conceptual framework of the game, the fourth outlines the technical specifications and key development decisions, and the fifth discusses potential uses and future expansions of the game and includes a link to access it.

1.1 Game overview

The game aims to raise awareness about the core principles of the P2Green project. Through an engaging mechanism, the player will learn concepts related to the innovative technologies and processes used in P2Green for collection and treatment of human sanitary waste and its transformation into fertilizer. Through play, participants gain an understanding of the crucial role that urine and faeces can have in sustainable resource management, and how shifting our sanitary waste practices can lead to meaningful environmental improvements. Through a motivating gameplay experience, the P2Green videogame aims to promote a behavioral change toward sustainable living, highlighting the importance of circular sanitary practices. The game is primarily targeted at the public from adults to youth that have an interest in getting an initial understanding of circular sanitary practices, the P2Green technologies and pilots.

To achieve this objective, the game integrates a series of informative slides about the general concept and methodology of the P2Green project, the recovery cycles use cases of the P2Green pilots, and the main impact indicators addressed by the P2Green technologies. The latter are organized in a catalog which includes a description and an impact score for each one, visible through interactive rollovers. The game also aims to illustrate P2Green’s potential impact within the regions involved and to depict a possible future shaped by an alternative sanitary system.

1.2 Gameplay mechanics

The gameplay is structured in two phases which are interrelated to each other. The first phase is a quiz-based system in which players, through answering multiple choice questions about the main topics of P2Green (e.g. P2Green technologies, the N&P cycle, etc.) earn coins that can be spent in phase two.

Phase two is a scenario-based interface which is characterized by a Menu that includes the catalogue of P2Green technologies grouped into three categories: Collection, Treatment, and Fertilizer, four impact indicators and a main scenario which represents the pilots of P2Green. Each technology included in the catalogue has a qualitative impact score assessed according to the four indicators, namely: Reversing Eutrophication, N&P collection capacity, Implementation Effort, Investment Cost. In this phase, the player, by using the coins earned in phase one, can “purchase” the P2Green technologies from the catalogue and drag and drop them in the scenario. Technologies are only selectable if they are relevant to the specific region, either already in use or realistically implementable.

When the player reaches a pre-defined impact score, the scenario changes, showing the impact of the player's choices. The scenario transitions from an initial baseline state of polluted environment to an environmentally enhanced version with lower eutrophication effects and reduction of chemical imported fertilizers.

A full list of questions included in the quiz-based system is provided in Table 1 in Annex, and a full catalogue of P2Green technologies, including their impact on the four indicators and their applicability to each pilot region, is provided in Table 2 in Annex. An image sequence showing the scenario evolution for each pilot is provided in Figure 1 in Annex (Gotland), Figure 2 in Annex (Spain) and Figure 3 in Annex (North German Plain).

1.3 Story and setting

The game is set across the three P2Green pilot regions: La Axarquía in Spain, the North German Plain, and Gotland in Sweden. Each pilot faces its own specific challenges: water scarcity in La Axarquía's mango and avocado plantations, peak tourism and Baltic Sea eutrophication in Gotland, and peak traffic and sanitation issues during festivals in the North German Plain. Each region also features its own suite of P2Green technologies allowing players to understand the technical processes behind each recovery solution and how they influence key environmental issues such as water scarcity, eutrophication, and diffuse pollution. The game scenarios for each region have been co-created together with the local partners of P2Green and are described here following.

North German Plain

The North German Plain initially lies beneath a haze of diffuse pollution, with a river choked by algal blooms and fish deaths. Heavy truck traffic to wastewater plants and the continued use of conventional fertilizers further strains the environment.

As circular sanitary systems are gradually introduced, the landscape begins to heal: the once murky river starts turning blue with reduced eutrophication, traffic decreases, and the remaining vehicles are smaller and more sustainable, reflecting a shift toward ecological balance.

In the fully restored scenario, the river runs crystal clear, free from eutrophication; traffic is minimal; cyclists and swimmers return; biodiversity thrives; and signage for the composting facility highlights the broad adoption of circular sanitation practices.

La Axarquía, Spain

The Axarquía region begins in severe water scarcity: soils are dry, mango and avocado orchards are stressed, reservoirs are nearly empty, chemical fertilizers remain widespread, waterways show signs of eutrophication, and farmers face rising fertilizer costs.

Over time, recovery takes shape: clean water flows through irrigation channels, soil moisture improves, orchards regain vitality, biodiversity reappears, and farmers' optimism grows. Violet reclaimed water pipes signal a shift toward sustainable irrigation practices.

In the final restored stage, a vivid blue river flows through fertile soil; mango and avocado trees stand lush and productive; biodiversity flourishes; farmers manage precise fertigation digitally; and an expanded network of purple pipes showcases the maturity of sustainable irrigation.

Gotland, Sweden

Gotland's coastline initially reflects environmental degradation driven by intense tourism, linear sanitary systems, and a dependence on external chemical fertilizers. The Baltic Sea's greenish tint signals ongoing eutrophication.

As circular sanitary systems are progressively implemented, conditions improve: reliance on imported fertilizers drops, the sea's green hue lightens as eutrophication nearly disappears, and both swimmers and marine species begin to return.

Ultimately, Gotland reaches strong ecological recovery: the Baltic Sea becomes clear and radiant, free from eutrophication; circular sanitary systems support sustainable tourism; water activities flourish; and marine life thrives once again.

1.4 Technical specifications

This subsection is divided into two parts, "Visual Identity" and "Software," which describe the technical decisions made during the development of the game.

1.4.1 Visual identity

The game uses a pixel-art visual style, a classic and recognizable game aesthetic. This style offers easy readability and lightweight graphics, making it highly suitable for web deployment and ensuring smooth performance. Pixel art emphasizes illustration and concept rather than realism, allowing players to focus on the game's ideas rather than visual complexity. The interface remains simple to avoid overwhelming players, especially important in a game with a strong educational component. Additionally, the pixel-art style is rooted in gaming history, evoking familiarity and a sense of playfulness that enhances player engagement.

1.4.2 Software

The game is a web-based tool that can be accessed by users through laptops, mobile phones, and tablets. The game is built using Unity 6.1 and deployed as WebGL on Unity's servers. For the visual assets, five base images for each scenario were generated in total. Three has been generated using an AI image generator (imagine.art with Nano Banana by Google AI studio). These served as benchmark stages for the initial condition, the condition where P2Green technologies begin to be applied, and the condition representing the upscaled implementation of P2Green solutions. Two intermediate images were then created in Photoshop to illustrate the transitions between these benchmark stages, resulting in a total of five images per scenario.

1.5 Conclusions

The P2GreeN videogame will be made available on the P2GreeN webpage through [this link](#) and will be used throughout the project during public events, such as conferences, workshops, etc. The current version can be expanded with extra multiple choice questions, by generating new scenarios for the three P2GreeN pilot regions or for other pilots and through the addition of other innovative technologies for circular sanitary waste management.

2 Annex

2.1 Table 1

	Question	Correct answer	Incorrect 01	Incorrect 02	Incorrect 03
Level 1	What everyday material can be used as a natural fertilizer instead of chemicals?	Human excreta	Processed wood chips	Charcoal powder	Filtered rainwater
	What is in urine and feces that is valuable?	Nitrogen and Phosphorus	Sulfur and carbon	Oxygen and iron	Calcium and phosphorus
	What currently happens to our feces and urine?	They are discharged either treated or untreated in our water bodies.	They are turned into fuel in treatment plants.	They are stored underground indefinitely.	They are recycled without treatment.
	What is the advantage of composting feces?	Producing nutrient-rich soil fertilizer and conserving water	Supporting controlled biological processes for increased emissions	Managing stable organic materials with high energy cost	Creating waste materials that demand frequent chemical treatment
	Are conventional fertilizers sustainable?	No, they generate polluted waterways, nutrient runoff, and the release of harmful greenhouse gas emissions	Yes, they support controlled applications while improving short-term yields	No, they reduce soil resilience and contribute to chemical dependencies	Yes, they maintain balanced outputs when managed under targeted programs
	What is a dry toilet?	A toilet where human excreta is collected without water.	A toilet that burns waste	A toilet using seawater	A chemical toilet with disinfectants
	What role does Nitrogen and Phosphorus play in nature?	They are critical for plant growth, crop yield, and overall soil fertility.	They cause soil degradation.	They reduce plant growth.	They are toxic to all crops.
	How can we save water resources? What do fertilizers do?	Reclaimed water for irrigation They provide nutrients in a concentrated form that plants can readily use.	Increasing chemical fertilizer usage They remove nutrients from soil and increase plant growth over time significantly.	Using no fertilizer They neutralize minerals in fields and block roots from absorbing available resources.	Building more nuclear reactors They filter contaminants from rivers and improve drinking water quality for households.
	How much fresh water is used by an average flushing?	6 to 9 liters	3 to 9 liters	1 to 1.5 liters	3 to 6 liters
	Level 2	How can we improve soil quality?	By adding organic matter like compost, practice crop rotation, and use cover crops.	By removing surface vegetation very frequently, avoid planting, and leave fields completely bare.	By compacting the ground with machinery, reduce pores, and limit movement of air.
Why is phosphorus considered a limited global resource?		Because it must be mined and it's non-renewable on human timescales	Because it can't be mined.	Because it's extracted from oceans.	Because plants consume it faster than what it's produced.
In which types of crops can urine-based fertilizers be safely used?		Vegetables, flowers, fruits and feed crops.	Protected forest species, invasive ornamentals, ornamental grasses and parkland trees.	Forestry seedlings, roadside vegetation, hedges and shade plants.	Recreational fields, mixed landscape beds, non-edible garden plants and turf areas.
What is the main environmental benefit of recycling nitrogen from wastewater?		It reduces the need for energy-intensive synthetic fertilizer production.	It increases pollution.	It reduces the need for intensive farming.	It reduces soil fertility.
Where can we use reclaimed water?		For irrigation of agricultural crops.	It is used for drinking water without treatment.	It is only suitable for cooling engines and agriculture.	It cannot be used for agriculture.
What are the three outputs of a wastewater treatment plant?		Treated effluent, sludge and gaseous emissions	Clean air, minerals, and sand.	Solid waste, oil, and metals.	Only water and carbon dioxide.
What can feces be used for?		Processed into nutrient-rich recycled fertilizer.	Used for energy storage.	Transformed into non-drinking water.	Nothing, they are full of pathogens.
What is a pathogen?		An organism that causes diseases.	A harmless organism that purifies soil	A fertilizer that boosts plant growth if correctly treated.	A natural vitamin found in compost.
How does resource recovery help to protect the environment?		By reducing waste sent to landfills and incinerators and saving energy.	By storing waste for future use without recycling.	By increasing the efficiency of waste disposal sites.	By focusing only on energy generation from waste, not on material reuse.
How much pee does an average adult generate per day?		1 to 1.5 liters	1.5 to 2 liters	2 to 3 liters	0.5 to 1 liter
Level 3	Is animal manure currently used for agriculture?	Yes, for agriculture as a fertilizer and soil amendment	Yes, but mainly as animal feed instead of soil fertilizer.	No, it is always disposed of to prevent soil contamination.	Yes, but only after chemical processing to remove nitrogen.
	Which of the P2Green technologies are used at festivals?	Dry toilets, closed and open urinals.	Chemical toilets with nutrient extraction systems.	Portable composting toilets without urine diversion.	Standard flush toilets connected to mobile tanks.
	What does a circular systemic solution mean?	A large-scale, integrated project that applies circular-economy principles to transform an entire local or regional system.	A project that focuses on reducing waste within a single sector rather than across all interconnected sectors.	A solution that reuses certain materials but does not address broader social or environmental interactions.	An initiative that prioritizes recycling programs without addressing wider structural changes.
	What are "dead zones"?	Areas in aquatic environments, such as bays and lakes, where oxygen levels drop so low that most marine life cannot survive	Regions where water becomes too hot for wildlife to enter	Places where tides stop moving and sediments accumulate	Natural spaces where aquatic animals migrate seasonally
	What is reclaimed water?	Treated effluent from waste water treatment plants.	Water collected directly from storm drains.	Water pumped from deep industrial mines.	Water skimmed from household surface runoff.
	What technology can help with drought in summers?	Water reclamation plant	Solar-powered mist cooling towers	Large-scale river diversion pumps	Deep underground ice storage systems
	What is Eutrophication?	The process where a body of water becomes excessively enriched with nutrients, and this excess leads to an algal bloom.	The natural cooling of ocean currents during winter seasons.	The gradual hardening of riverbeds due to mineral deposits.	The formation of new wetlands through sediment layering.
	What are the health and safety benefits of the conversion of human excreta into safe bio based fertilizers?	The risk of spreading faecal-borne pathogens and the dependency on synthetic fertilisers with their associated environmental impacts	The process increases exposure to airborne contaminants and requires additional protective equipment.	The conversion raises the likelihood of chemical residues accumulating in agricultural soils.	The use of such fertilizers leads to less uncertainty in managing toxic substances during farming activities.
	How "peak" activities such as tourism or festivals impact the environment?	High pollution and wastewater plants get overloaded.	They reduce local traffic and fuel consumption.	They stabilize water demand across all seasons.	They decrease waste output due to shorter stays.
	What is a UDDT?	Urine diverting dry toilet.	Under-drain disposal tank.	Ultra-dry drainage trough.	Universal decentralized treatment.
Level 4	Is it safe to use urine fertilizer?	Yes, if the urine has been treated with P2Green technologies	Yes, when urine is stored openly.	Yes, when urine is mixed directly with untreated sludge.	Yes, when urine is diluted with seawater prior to use.
	What is Aurin?	An urine-based fertilizer	A chemical fertilizer	A synthetic soil-enhancing polymer	A commercial pesticide blend
	What is a "kissamaja"?	An unisex urinal	A portable hand washing dispenser	A combined shower-and-toilet booth	A self-cleaning compost bin
	Which percentage of nutrients is currently discharged in sanitary waste in Europe?	25% for Nitrogen, and about 50% for Phosphorus	10% for Nitrogen, and roughly 5% for Phosphorus	60% for Nitrogen, and around 80% for Phosphorus	3% for Nitrogen, and nearly 12% for Phosphorus
	What is the smart-fertigation tool used for?	Optimise use of water and nutrients in reclaimed water.	Measure wind direction for irrigation timing.	Estimate crop prices for market planning.	Monitor soil color changes for harvest decisions.
	Which one has more Nitrogen?	Urine	Feces	Reclaimed water	Filtered groundwater
	What is Granurin?	An urine-based fertilizer.	A clay-based soil binder.	A powdered mineral additive.	A slow-release pesticide coating.
	How much nitrogen can be recovered from sanitary waste in the EU?	10360 tons/day	150 tons/day	42000 tons/year	800 kilograms/month
	What are the energy needs for mineral fertilizer?	About 8 gigajoule of fossil energy per hectare of wheat.	About 2 kilojoules of energy per truckload of grain.	About 15 watts of power per tonne of fertilizer.	About 6 megawatt-hours per household each winter.
	What is the Haber Bosch process?	A chemical method for Nitrogen fertilizer production.	A filtration technique for seawater purification.	A thermal process for melting industrial slag.	A mechanical method for grinding mineral rock.

Table 1: List of questions per level.

2.2 Table 2

Technology category	Technology			Indicators				Tokens	Scenario of application		
	Name	Image	Text (Appearing when rolling over tech)	Reversing eutrophication	N&P collection capacity	Implementation effort	Investment cost		Coins	Gotland Sweden	La Axarquía region, Spain
Collection	Unisex urinal		Kissamajas is a unisex dry urinal that anyone can use. Instead of peeing in the sea, people pee in the kissamaja, where their urine is transformed into nutrient rich fertiliser.	1	3	1	1	40	x	x	x
Collection	Urine-diverting toilet Scaling up Urine collection from event to all buildings and houses		Urine-diverting flush (or dry) toilets enable collection from buildings and houses too.	2	4	3	3	60	x		
Collection	Open urinal		This are male open urinals. On Gotland, Touchdown (a toilet rental company), has partnered with Sanitation360 so that the collected urine can be processed into a sustainable fertiliser.	1	3	1	1	40	x	x	x
Collection	Lapee		Lapee is the urinal for women and gender non-conforming people who squat to pee. It ensures a clean, safe and quick experience for everyone.	1	3	1	1	40	x	x	x
Collection	Dry toilets		Dry toilets are designed to recycle the nutrients in your waste and use them to build healthy soil. Through controlled composting, the waste is transformed into hygienically safe, nutrient-rich humus fertilizer, which we then apply to fields as part of field trials.	1	3	2	1	40	x	x	x
Fertilizer	Dry fertilizer granule sacs		The urine-based fertilizer contains the same type and concentration of plant nutrients found in commercial fertilizers. We produce a fertilizer that can be used with the same equipment as conventional pelletized fertilizer to make urine fertilizer use more accessible.	3	0	1	1	20	x		
Fertilizer	Smart fertigation tool		The Smart Fertigation Tool continuously monitors the nutrients in reclaimed water and uses this information to adjust irrigation and fertilizer doses in real time. By matching water and nutrients to the exact needs of mango and avocado crops, farmers reduce fertilizer use, prevent pollution, and improve the quality of their fruits.	3	1	2	2	40		x	
Fertilizer	Aurin fertilizer tanks		Aurin is a universal fertilizer made from human urine. In VunaNexus urine treatment plants urine is converted into fertilizer: drug residues, hormones, and germs are removed, while the nutrients remain.	3	0	1	1	20			x
Treatment	Government support		Government support is needed to enable the scale of urine fertiliser production. Such support can be at EU or national level and include: mandating nutrient recycling from wastewater, legalisation the selling and use of urine fertiliser, new building code that requires nutrient recovering systems, subsidies for implementing urine-diverting systems.	4	4	4	1	100	x		
Treatment	Urine treatment plant		The collected urine is processed into a solid fertiliser that works with conventional farming equipment.	3	1	2	2	80	x		
Treatment	Water reclamation plant		The water reclamation plant provides an advanced treatment to the treated wastewater from the municipal WWTP using disc filtration and ozone disinfection. This additional treatment ensures the removal of pathogens and contaminants, transforming wastewater into a nutrient-rich effluent.	4	4	4	4	80		x	
Treatment	Composting container		Container composting means, above all, an increase in convenience and logistical flexibility. Equipped with intelligent software solutions, active process monitoring and odor control thanks to an encapsulated design, our container technology is a demonstration of state-of-the-art solutions for waste management.	3	1	2	3	80	x	x	x
Treatment	Composting treatment plant by Goldeimer		At Goldeimer's recycling plant, a hygienic recycled fertilizer is produced through safe composting.	3	1	4	3	90			x
Treatment	Urine treatment plant to liquid fertilizer		The system from VunaNexus, converts urine via a bioreactor into a liquid fertiliser. This is especially relevant for horticulture, gardens, and parks.	4	1	2	3	90			x

Table 2: Catalogue of P2Green solutions.

2.3 Figure 1

Figure 1

Figure 1: Scenario sequence for Gotland, Sweden.

2.4 Figure 2

Figure 2: Scenario sequence for La Axarquía, Spain.

2.5 Figure 3

Figure 3: Scenario sequence for North German Plain, Germany.

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